

Bohm Aharonov Effect Part II

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In this note, we consider the Hamiltonian $\frac{1}{2m} (\mathbf{p} - e/c \mathbf{A})(\mathbf{p} - e/c \mathbf{A}) W = E W$ ((1)) in the situation where there is no magnetic field even though $A(x)$ still exists. Thus, if there is no force, one might expect to have a free particle which satisfies $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W = E W$ and yields a free particle spatial density. Thus, one might guess the solution to ((1)) should be a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ikx)$ with perhaps a phase added. Such a phase does not affect spatial density W^*W . One may solve ((1)) using the assumption that $d/dx A(x) = 0$ (used in the literature (1)) to find: $W = W_{\text{free}}(x) \exp(i e/\hbar c \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$. Thus, one treats this phase as if one had $\exp(i K x)$ where $K=A(x)$. A second derivative d/dx brings down $i A(x)$ again. In previous notes, we suggested that a potential is stochastic and may be written as: $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. If one expands the terms in ((1)) and uses $d/dx A = 0$, one obtains a momentum dependent potential. This potential should be physical, we argue, because it applies to cases where there is a magnetic field as well as to the case here where there is not. Thus, the potential should give hits of the form $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ as well as couple to $d/dx W$. In other words, we argue these hits are real whether or not average force is zero. The effect of such hits is to create a momentum distribution at each x : $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. There is forward and backward motion, but the average kinetic energy $\langle x \rangle + V(x) = E$ at each point where: $\text{kinetic energy}(x) = [\sum_p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x)$. Given that average kinetic energy should be $p^2/2m$ for a free particle (if the potential yields no hits), one may consider a phase $\exp(i K(x) x)$ multiplied by $W_{\text{free}}(x)$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This seems to imply a shifted velocity i.e. a local collective velocity of $K(x)$ where $K(x)$ happens to equal $A(x)$ in this case. Matters, however, seem to be more complicated as we consider a microscopic coupling of $\exp(ikx)$ terms from both $W_{\text{free}}(x)$ and $\exp(i \text{Bohm Aharonov})$ phase just as there may be a coupling between $W = W_0 W_1$ where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state and $W_1(x)$ represents the effects of an interacting substance (e.g. a photon or phonon).

Bohm Aharonov and Mapping to a Free Particle

The Schrodinger equation for a particle in a magnetic field is (1):

$$\frac{1}{2m} (\mathbf{p} - e/c \mathbf{A})(\mathbf{p} - e/c \mathbf{A}) W = E W \quad ((1))$$

One may expand the terms in this equation to obtain a momentum dependent potential assuming $dA/dx=0$ i.e. A changes very slowly.

$$\frac{1}{2m} p^* p + \frac{1}{2m} (e/c A)^2 W - \frac{1}{m} e/c A p W = E W \quad ((2))$$

In some cases, there may be no magnetic field (curl A), yet A and the potential in ((2)) still exist. If there is no force, one may argue one has a free particle with a free particle spatial density i.e. 1. This implies ((2)) may be written as:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W_{\text{free}} \exp(i K(x) x)] = E W \quad ((3))$$

One may solve ((2)) with the assumption $dA/dx=0$ (as in (1)) to find:

$$K(x) = ie/\hbar \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1.$$

This is the Bohm-Aharonov phase which is picked up even if a particle moves through a region with no magnetic field (and hence no force). A phase shift seems to imply a time delay or interaction. At first this may seem like a paradox, given that average force is zero. We have argued in (2), however, that $V(x)$ is only an average. It may have components yielding forces to the left and right at different times with a net force of zero. The particle, however, still feels forces at different times which are associated with $\exp(ikx)$ terms in the potential. Thus, having no average force may still mean an interaction which “delays” the free particle. The momentum dependent potential in ((2)) is physical (i.e. gives hits) for the case of a magnetic field (causing a force), so it seems it should still be physical and yield hits (based on $\exp(ikx)$) for a zero magnetic field.

At this point, one may argue that a free wave has one momentum value i.e. $W_{\text{free}}(x)=\exp(ipx)$. For a particle in a box, the wavefunction is $\sin(px)$, but p is only an average value. For the particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the step function of the potential at the walls written as a Fourier transform brings in all momentum components $\exp(ipx)$ (3). Thus, if there is a square well potential, the Fourier potential stirs up all $\exp(ipx)$ and there is a probability to have one with a momentum which may penetrate the barrier. The $V(x)$ of the barrier is only an average as well. Thus, for the potential containing the magnetic field $A(x)$ in ((2)), we argue that there may be a probability distribution at each x i.e. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ ((4)) with different $\exp(ipx)$ components such that the average yields $\exp(i p_{\text{ave}} x)$. Thus, the effect of the momentum dependent potential at each x is to shift each momentum p in ((4)) by $A(x)$ which is taken to be a local constant.

One may next consider the effect of the kinetic energy terms $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_{\text{free}}(x) \exp(i e/\hbar \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$. Only one is $p^2/2m$, the free particle kinetic energy. The other terms cancel the potential terms to yield $p^2/2m = E$. Here $dA/dx=0$ is used as in (1). Thus, there must be physical meaning to:

$$p^2/2m + \frac{1}{2m} (e/\hbar A)^2 - \frac{1}{m} e/c A \frac{d}{dx} W_{\text{free}} \quad ((5))$$

as kinetic energy. Now, on average $\hbar/i \frac{d}{dx} W_{\text{free}} = p_{\text{ave}} \exp(i p_{\text{ave}} x)$ so if $A(x)$ is considered to be constant at each x (assumption of (1)), then ((5)) is equivalent to:

$$(p - e/cA)(p - e/cA)/2m \quad ((6))$$

with A changing at each x . Imagine one has a particle in a box. The speed of the box is A while the speed relative to a wall in the box is $-p$. The kinetic energy relative to the ground is $\frac{(p+A)^2}{2m}$ while $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ is the kinetic energy relative to the box. In such a picture, the particle does not interact with the box. In (2) , however, there is an interaction which is the negative of $\frac{1}{2m} (p+A)(p+A) - \frac{1}{2m} p^2$. We do not wish to consider such a picture, however, because p represents p average. There exist all of the $\exp(ikx)$ present at different times creating the average $\exp(i \text{pave } x)$ wavefunction. These different $\exp(i k x)$ interact with the potential of (2) , yet the interesting thing is that they interact within the overall kinetic energy as well to cancel the interaction of the potential. How is this possible in a physical sense? Certainly interactions with a potential make sense, but how may one argue that there are kinetic energy interactions?

To try to deal with this issue, consider the general idea of a product wavefunction $W_0(x)W_1(x)$. An example might be to have $W_0(x)$ represent the ground state of a system. In such a case, $W_0(x)$ represents a physical state which may interact with a "disturbance" (sound or light etc) to create a new physical state $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$. If one argues that the new state may physically retain the identity of the ground state $W_0(x)$, then one could envision a coupling of kinetic energies e.g. $\exp(i k_0 x) \exp(i k_1 x)$ where the first factor is a momentum state from W_0 and the second, one from W_1 . The two couple to create a momentum state of k_0+k_1 which has a kinetic energy (with relative probabilities) of $\frac{(k_0+k_1)^2}{2m} a(k_0) b(k_1) \exp(i k_0 x) \exp(i k_1 x)$. Thus, physical coupling of $\exp(ikx)$ terms, just as in the case of a potential coupling with $W(x)$ may occur. In the kinetic energy case, these couplings lead to "new" momentum states $\exp(i (k_0+k_1)x)$ yielding their respective kinetic energy. Note that if one considers k_0+k_1 and $-k_0-k_1$ and $a(k)$ and $b(k)$ are even functions, then one has a combined term of $\cos((k_0+k_1)x)$. Thus, the coupling leads to physical behaviour governing the average kinetic energy at different x points. This kinetic energy coupling seems to be as physical as $V(x) W(x)$ coupling.

Returning to the electromagnetic case, let us write the kinetic energy coupling terms as:

$$\text{KE coupling} = \sum_k \left[\sum_{k_0} \frac{1}{2m} a(k_0)b(k-k_0) \right] k^2 \exp(ikx) + \sum_{k_0} \left[c(k-k_0) a(k_0) \right] \exp(ikx)$$

Here $a(k)$ represents the Fourier weight associated with W_{free} , $b(k)$ that associated with $\exp(i e/\hbar \int A(x) dx)$ and $c(k)$ that associated with the potential. (Here we are simplifying because the potential is actually momentum dependent.) The point seems to be that if $b(0)=1$, only $\sum_k \frac{1}{2m} a(k) k^2 \exp(ikx)$ remains after cancellation. Thus, all actual coupling terms from both the kinetic energy and potential energy cancel leaving only a non-coupled term $a(k)$ (k does not couple with a momentum of 0). This does not mean that complicated motion is not occurring. If it were not, there would be no delays and hence no phase shift, we argue.

Case of a Constant Potential

As a final example, consider a free particle with momentum k which travels a distance L through a constant potential V_1 . There is no force associated with this potential. Consider another free particle with momentum k which travels a distance L through a constant potential of V_2 . The spatial density of the two is the same, but we argue that in the free wavefunction $W(x) = \exp(ikx)$, k only represents an average momentum. Thus, we argue that $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and that these $\exp(ipx)$ terms interact with the Fourier expansion of $V_i = \sum_k V_i(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, the force is only zero on average, but each potential gives hits to the right and left with different weights of $V_i(k)$. Thus, the microscopic motion of the particle through both regions is different even though the spatial density is the same. If one considers $\exp(i \text{Energy } t)$, then the particle in region one has $\exp(i(k^2/2m + V_1)t)$ while that in region two, $\exp(i(k^2/2m + V_2)t)$. Thus, examining the time dependent part of the wavefunction implies a phase shift between the two paths. This is exactly the phase shift given by the adiabatic theory, even though this is not an adiabatic expansion problem as no parameter is being changed. Thus, we argue that the time dependent part of the wavefunction $\exp(iEt)$ is physical and if the energy is different because of V_1 versus V_2 , then physical cycling is different and this cycling is related to various $\exp(ikx)$ terms and their reaction with the potential. Thus, the free wave function $\exp(ikx)$ only represents average behaviour ($k = k_{ave}$) and one, it seems, should have a phase shift $\exp(iEt)$ which may be related to space because $x = kt$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to investigate what we believe to be the microscopic, physical meaning of the Bohm Aharonov phase shift factor $\exp(ie/c \hbar \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$. We argue one may have physical coupling of $\exp(ikx)$ terms from a product wavefunction i.e. $W_{free}(x) \exp(ie/\hbar \int_{x_1=0}^x A(x_1) dx_1)$ namely: $\sum_{k, k_1} a(k-k_1) b(k_1) \exp(ikx)$ where $a(k)$ is associated with $W_{free}(x)$ and $b(k)$ with $\exp(\text{Bohm Aharonov})$. This coupling leads to "new" momenta with their respective kinetic energies. The Bohm Aharonov potential (even though it involves a magnetic field of 0) couples with W and $d/dx W$. The various coupling terms cancel, leaving on the uncoupled kinetic energy piece $a(k)b(0) \exp(ikx)$ and its associated kinetic energy $k^2/2m$. We assume $b(0)=1$. We also suggest that $\exp(i \text{pave } x)$ for a free particle really consists of many physical $\exp(i k x)$ which interact with the Fourier expansion of even a constant potential. Thus, "free" particles travelling through space may pick up various phases if there are physical constant potentials present which yield no average force. One, however, has to be careful as to the physical coupling of $W(x)$ with the potential.

References

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